

FREEDOM OF EXPRESSION IN THE JURISPRUDENCE OF THE SUPREME FEDERAL COURT

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ABSTRACT

The article analyzes the right to freedom of expression in the jurisprudence of the Brazilian Supreme Court, investigating the limits to this fundamental right provided for in the Federal Constitution of 1988. The study uses the dialectical method and bibliographical and jurisprudential research, collating important decisions of the Federal Supreme Court on the subject. As a result, it is found that there are several restrictions on freedom of expression, since it is not an absolute or unlimited right. Thus, the use of this constitutional right to propagate hate speech or discrimination, disseminate fake news during the electoral process, incite animosity between the Armed Forces and the Branches of the Union, call for the overthrow of the Democratic State of Law, among other prohibitions, is prohibited.

Keywords: Freedom of expression; jurisprudence; Supreme Federal Court.

INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this investigation is to analyze the evolution of the right to freedom of expression in the jurisprudence of the Brazilian Supreme Court. This matter is important because it allows us to assess the scope and limits of this fundamental right.

To this end, the dialectical method and bibliographic and jurisprudential research are adopted, comparing representative and recent judgments in the Court, specifically from the beginning of the 21st century to the present day. The research is based on three axes: *i*) freedom of expression in the 1988 Federal Constitution; *ii*) freedom of expression versus other constitutional rights; and *iii*) Supreme Federal Court jurisprudence on the subject.

1. Freedom of Expression in the 1988 Federal Constitution

The 1988 Federal Constitution, founded on a Democratic State of Law, expressly enshrines the fundamental right to freedom of expression. This fundamental right constitutes an inherent prerogative not only of a "State of Law"—meaning the Public Power governed by law and the norms that comprise the legal system—but also of a "Democratic State"—an expression that designates the Public Power governed by democratic values, notably individual rights, equality, the holding of free elections, the alternation of power, political tolerance, etc. Thus, Brazil adheres to these principles, as they are inherent to the regime then in force.

Given its notorious relevance, the current Constitution addresses freedom of expression in several provisions, such as Article 5, item IV, which declares: "the expression of thought is free, anonymity being prohibited," as well as Article 5, item VI, which asserts: "freedom of conscience and belief is inviolable, the free exercise of religious worship being ensured and the protection of places of worship and their liturgies being guaranteed, in accordance with the law." Similarly, Article 5, item IX ensures: "the expression of intellectual, artistic, scientific and communication activity is free, regardless of censorship or license"; as well as Article 220: "the expression of thought, creation, expression and information, in any form, process or medium, shall not suffer any restriction, subject to the provisions of this Constitution" (Brazilian Federal Constitution of 1988).

As can be seen, freedom of expression is guaranteed at the constitutional level by several articles, having broad application in various aspects of an individual's life, especially in relation to other individuals, being an elementary precept of a pluralistic society. However, in the exercise of this principle, it can sometimes clash with other rights that are also of constitutional importance, which is the subject of the next topic.

2. Freedom of Expression *Versus* Other Constitutional Rights

According to the Constitution, freedom of expression is a fundamental right, as it is part of the catalog of rights provided for in Title II of the 1988 Federal Constitution. However, "fundamental rights" are correlated with "fundamental duties," that is, they are linked to obligations of a constitutional nature. Constitutional duties relate to passive legal situations, since citizens have duties towards the community, and almost all Constitutions provide for a series of duties for individuals, such as paying taxes, performing military service, among others

(MIRANDA, 1998). Thus, constitutional duties constitute a counterpart to the prerogatives conferred, in addition to establishing a limit to the respective rights.

Furthermore, freedom of expression is a constitutional principle. According to Alexy, principles are optimization mandates, characterized by "being able to be satisfied to varying degrees and by the fact that the appropriate measure of their satisfaction depends not only on factual possibilities but also on legal possibilities." If the principle of freedom of expression clashes with another constitutional principle, a balancing must be made; that is, it must be assessed which principle takes precedence over the other under certain conditions, according to the weight of each (ALEXY, 2008, pp. 90-94). For Ronald Dworkin, principles possess a dimension that rules do not have, which consists of the dimension of weight or importance. "When principles intersect, whoever resolves the conflict must take into account the relative strength of each" (DWORKIN, 2010, pp. 36-43).

Thus, the exercise of a fundamental right may conflict with the exercise of another right of equal nature or with constitutionally protected legal goods. In this sense, Canotilho clarifies that the *authentic conflict* A collision of fundamental rights occurs when "the exercise of a fundamental right by its holder clashes with the exercise of a fundamental right by another holder," not as a crossing or accumulation of rights, but rather as a "clash" or "genuine conflict." A collision of rights in an improper sense occurs "when the exercise of a fundamental right clashes with other constitutionally protected goods" (CANOTILHO, 1999, p. 1191). In such cases, a weighing must be done according to the set of facts surrounding them; that is, the interpreter must assess the weight of the conflicting constitutional principles, assigning the respective value according to the peculiarities of the specific case.

Daniel Sarmento clarifies that the collision between fundamental rights is a common phenomenon, especially in extensive constitutions, of a "compromise nature, and composed of many precepts enshrined in open language," since "the extent of the Constitution increases the possibility of conflicts, because the more norms there are, the greater the possibility of tension between them" (SOUZA NETO; SARMENTO, 2016, p. 495).

Thus, the right to freedom of expression can clash with other rights – and sometimes even violate them – also of constitutional importance. By way of illustration, the abuse of freedom of expression can: *i* – violate human dignity, enshrined in Article 1, item III, of the 1988 Brazilian Constitution (for example, denying someone the status of a person because of their ethnic characteristics); *ii* – incur discrimination and racism, prohibited conduct that must be criminally repressed, according to Article 3, item IV in conjunction with Article 5, items XLI and XLII of the 1988 Brazilian Constitution (such as offending someone's honor or humiliating

them because of their skin color or phenotypic traits); *iii* – deny the right to equality between genders (for example, advocating the superiority of men over women); *iv* – to advocate torture, cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment, conduct which is prohibited by Article 5, item III of the 1988 Federal Constitution (for example, encouraging the beating or mutilation of body parts of convicts as part of the punishment for committing crimes); *v* – to violate the intimacy, private life, honor and image of individuals (such as clandestinely installing cameras inside someone's residence to later disseminate and comment on the videos to their detriment).

The distortion of the right to freedom of expression can also result in: *vi* – advocating the creation of associations for illicit purposes, which is prohibited by article 5, item XVII of the 1988 Federal Constitution (such as inciting the formation of anti-Semitic groups, criminal organizations, or vigilantes to privately avenge crimes in general); *vii* – advocating the establishment of a dictatorship, in violation of the principle of popular sovereignty and the democratic regime, according to article 1, sole paragraph, in conjunction with article 17, caput, of the 1988 Federal Constitution (for example, calling on the population to destroy public property, commit looting, acts of terrorism, or promote social chaos with the intention of modifying the republican regime or removing the legitimately elected government); *viii* – making an apology for pedophilia, whose ignoble act is peremptorily prohibited by the Constitution, it being the duty of all society to protect children and adolescents, according to article 227 of the 1988 Federal Constitution; etc.

Indeed, freedom of expression, if not used properly, can degenerate into an instrument that causes various violations of other fundamental rights, since the 1988 Federal Constitution enshrines several legal prerogatives; that is, when exercising their right to freedom of expression, an individual cannot violate other rights and values also enshrined in the Constitution, such as the right to life, liberty, dignity, equality, honor, image, privacy, private property, popular sovereignty, the Democratic Rule of Law, etc.

It should be emphasized that freedom of expression is a "fundamental right." However, "rights" are not absolute, that is, they are not unrestricted or exercised without limits. First, because "right" is the legal faculty existing under the terms of the norm, that is, according to the normative scope. In this case, the right is delimited by the framework that surrounds it, that is, by the set of possibilities existing in the legal statement. Secondly, no right derogates from another, nor is it superior to it a priori, that is, freedom of expression does not revoke or take precedence, by itself, over the right to equality, the right to dignity, the right to honor, the right to privacy, etc. Thirdly, fundamental rights – among which is freedom of expression – must be exercised by their holder in respect for the other guarantees enshrined in the text of the 1988

Federal Constitution, and must also be mindful of promoting their objectives, such as promoting the well-being of all, without prejudice based on origin, color, age, sex, or any other form of discrimination, in accordance with Article 3, item IV of the Magna Carta. In other words, the right to freedom of expression has not only legal limits, but also ethical ones. This is the understanding of the Supreme Federal Court: (STF, MS 23452/RJ)

In the Brazilian constitutional system, there are no rights or guarantees that are absolute, because reasons of significant public interest or requirements derived from the principle of coexistence of freedoms legitimize, even if exceptionally, the adoption, by state bodies, of measures restricting individual or collective prerogatives, provided that the terms established by the Constitution itself are respected. The constitutional statute of public freedoms, in outlining the legal regime to which they are subject – and considering the ethical foundation that informs them – allows for legal limitations to be imposed on them, intended, on the one hand, to protect the integrity of the social interest and, on the other, to ensure the harmonious coexistence of freedoms, since no right or guarantee can be exercised to the detriment of public order or with disrespect for the rights and guarantees of third parties.

Therefore, freedom of expression must respect other fundamental rights, which are also guaranteed in the 1988 Constitution. Below, we will examine some important rulings from the Supreme Federal Court that have defined the contours of this right.

3. SUPREME COURT CASE LAW ON THE SUBJECT

3.1. *Habeas Corpus* (HC)

In a judgment on September 17, 2023, the Brazilian Supreme Federal Court analyzed Habeas Corpus No. 82,424/RS, the case of Siegfried Ellwanger v. Werner Becker, which dealt with freedom of expression, racism, and antisemitism. In this case, the defendant was prosecuted for authoring works that conveyed antisemitic ideas and denied the historical occurrence of the Holocaust. The *habeas corpus petition* alleged the right to freedom of expression, but the Supreme Court denied the order on the grounds that freedom of expression does not encompass the right to incite racism. In this judgment, the Supreme Court also expressly declared that there is no subdivision of the human race, as it is a single race. (STF, HC No. 82424/RS).

3. Human race. Subdivision. Non-existence. With the definition and mapping of the human genome, scientifically there are no distinctions between humans, whether by skin type, eye shape, height, hair, or any other physical characteristics, since all qualify as the human species. There are no biological differences between human beings. In essence, they are all the same. 4. Race

and racism. The division of human beings into races results from a purely political-social process. From this assumption originates racism, which, in turn, generates discrimination and segregationist prejudice. 5. Foundation of the core thought of National Socialism that Jews and Aryans form distinct races. The former would be an inferior, nefarious, and infectious race, characteristics sufficient to justify segregation and extermination: irreconcilable with the ethical and moral standards defined in the Political Charter of Brazil and the contemporary world, under which the democratic state is built and harmonized. Stigmas that in themselves evidence the crime of racism. This conception violates the principles upon which human society is built and organized, based on the respectability and dignity of the human being and their peaceful coexistence within society. 19. Indeed, the division of human beings into races stems from a socio-political process originating from human intolerance. This resulted in racial prejudice. Since there is no scientific basis for dividing humanity into races, any discriminatory action against the species becomes even more odious. As scientifically evidenced, all humans inhabiting the planet, whether poor, rich, white, black, yellow, Jewish, or Muslim, belong to a single race, which is the human species, or the human race. This ratifies not only the equality of human beings, highlighted in international human rights norms, but also the foundations of the Pentateuch or Torah concerning the origin of humankind.

Indeed, this ruling by the Supreme Court is highly relevant, not only for imposing clear limits on freedom of expression, but also for its scientifically grounded response to racism. In other words, incitement to hatred and discrimination profoundly violates the legal order, and has no basis in science, given that the human race is one, making the purported classification into categories and, consequently, the nefarious practice of belittling others, unacceptable.

Therefore, the aforementioned ruling restricted freedom of expression to prevent its abuse by individuals, since this prerogative must be exercised within constitutional norms and principles, and not to commit serious violations of human rights.

3.2. Extraordinary Appeal

Extraordinary Appeal No. 511.961/SP, judged in 2009, debated the non-reception of Article 4, item V, of Decree-Law No. 972/1969 by the 1988 Federal Constitution, which required a higher education diploma, registered by the Ministry of Education, as a requirement for practicing the profession of journalist. The Supreme Federal Court understood that the aforementioned rule simultaneously violated the freedoms of profession, expression, and information (Article 5, IX and XIII, and Article 220, caput and § 1, CF/1988), which is why it declared the non-reception of Article 4, item V, of Decree-Law No. 972/1969, due to its material incompatibility with the postulates of the 1988 Federal Constitution.

In its reasoning, the Supreme Federal Court explained that journalism is a profession that stands out due to its close link to the full exercise of freedom of expression and communication, with journalism being a manifestation of the continuous, professional, and remunerated dissemination of thought and information. In other words, it is an activity directly linked to these factors, so that requiring a university degree to practice this profession constitutes a restriction incompatible with the constitutionally guaranteed freedoms of expression and information. (STF RE nº 511.961)

In this ruling, it is clear that the Supreme Federal Court has given greater scope to the right to freedom of expression, interpreting it as a way for individuals to work in their respective fields. In other words, it is not only about freely disseminating ideas and information, but also refers to the possibility of broadly exercising professions related to journalism. Therefore, the challenged norm was deemed incompatible with the current Constitution, and consequently, the aforementioned requirement is not enforceable.

Furthermore, the ruling upheld the principle of greater effectiveness of fundamental rights insofar as it broadened the right to freedom of expression to include the exercise of professional activities, provided that such activity does not constitute an offense or violation of the rights of others, thus making the measure appropriate to the constitutional context. Therefore, the judgment resulting from Extraordinary Appeal No. 511.961/SP broadened the right to freedom of expression, conferring greater effectiveness to this fundamental right.

Also noteworthy is Extraordinary Appeal No. 1,010,606/RJ, judged in 2021, which analyzed the right to freedom of expression versus the right to be forgotten. This case concerned the right of family members of a deceased person, a victim of a crime, to receive monetary compensation for the unauthorized use of the victim's image in a television program. The victim's family members asserted their right to be forgotten regarding the tragic event – based on the right to human dignity and the inviolability of honor and privacy – since the disclosure caused them repeated suffering. The Supreme Federal Court denied the request, stating that "the passage of time, in itself, does not have the power to transform a publication or data contained therein from lawful to unlawful," and that "the provision or application of the right to be forgotten infringes upon freedom of expression." Regarding this issue, the STF established the following thesis: (STF RE 1010606/RJ)

The idea of a right to be forgotten, understood as the power to prevent, due to the passage of time, the dissemination of truthful facts or data lawfully obtained and published in analog or digital media, is incompatible with the Constitution. Any excesses or abuses in the exercise of freedom of expression and information must be analyzed on a case-by-case basis, based on

constitutional parameters – especially those relating to the protection of honor, image, privacy, and personality in general – and the express and specific legal provisions in the criminal and civil spheres.

This process is significant because the Supreme Federal Court confronted the right to privacy – and the corollary right to be forgotten – with the right to freedom of expression, deciding in favor of the latter. In other words, in weighing these two fundamental rights, the Supreme Court understood that the right to freedom of expression carries greater weight in the specific case, and therefore gave it precedence.

3.3. Claim of Non-Compliance with a Fundamental Precept (ADPF)

On April 30, 2009, the Brazilian Supreme Court (STF) ruled on ADPF No. 130, which dealt with the non-reception of Federal Law No. 5,250, of February 9, 1967, known as the "Press Law." In this case, the Supreme Court upheld the request to declare the complete non-reception of provisions of the law, in observance of freedom of expression, the right to information, free artistic, scientific, intellectual and communicational expression, as well as journalistic and press freedom and their precedence over other personality rights, given that they are essential prerogatives for the functioning of democracy. (STF ADPF No. 130/DF)

In this case, the Supreme Federal Court applied the principle of maximum effectiveness of fundamental rights, giving a broader and more favorable interpretation to the exercise of the postulates inherent in the freedom of communication enshrined in the 1988 Constitution. Thus, the aforementioned process did not concern a collision of fundamental rights, but rather overturned the regulations established by the State during the military regime. It is important to note that when freedom of expression concerns its application in a broader scope, the Supreme Court commonly rules in favor of the action, whereas when it comes to a conflict between fundamental rights, the right to freedom of expression does not have primacy on its own. In other words, this postulate is carefully analyzed in relation to the other constitutional legal goods at stake, and may even be disregarded in such cases.

It should be noted that on June 15, 2011, the Brazilian Supreme Court (STF) also addressed an important issue related to freedom of expression in the context of a Claim of Non-Compliance with Fundamental Precept. This is because in ADPF No. 187, the Supreme Court decided that peaceful public demonstrations in favor of the decriminalization of drugs do not constitute a crime, since the conduct is protected by the right to assembly and freedom of expression, essential to the preservation of democracy. (STF ADPF No. 187)

As can be seen, the aforementioned rulings have broadened the right to freedom of expression, giving it greater constitutional effectiveness, and there is no conflict of fundamental rights here.

3.4. Direct Action of Unconstitutionality

In Direct Action of Unconstitutionality No. 7,261/DF, judged on December 19, 2023, the Supreme Federal Court analyzed the right to freedom of expression in the face of disinformation capable of harming the integrity of the electoral process. In this process, the STF deemed valid the normative elaboration and the police power exercised by the Superior Electoral Court during electoral propaganda, since the aforementioned specialized court has dealt with disinformation through repeated jurisprudential precedents and normative acts over the years. Thus, the act of an agent disseminating false news has the capacity to occupy all public space, ultimately restricting the circulation of ideas and the free exercise of the right to information by voters. "The phenomenon of disinformation disseminated through the internet, if not monitored by the electoral authority, has the power to restrict the free and conscious formation of the voter's will." (STF ADI No. 7261/DF)

This process stands out because freedom of expression cannot be used to spread fake news and undermine the integrity of the electoral process; that is, the free circulation of ideas cannot be used by the holder to disseminate misinformation or manipulate the truth of events with the aim of harming other candidates. In this case, the resolutions of the Superior Electoral Court safeguard the integrity of the election and the proper conduct of candidates for elective office, preventing dishonest and manipulative conduct regarding the facts disclosed in the elections.

Thus, freedom of expression must respect society, and the abusive use of this right by its holder is prohibited.

3.5. Direct Action of Unconstitutionality by Omission (ADO)

In Direct Action of Unconstitutionality by Omission (ADO) No. 26, judged on June 13, 2019, the Supreme Federal Court analyzed the omission of the National Congress in criminalizing homophobic conduct. In this process, the Court ruled in favor of the request made by the Popular Socialist Party (PPS) to recognize the unconstitutionality by omission and determine the application to homotransphobic conduct of the norm that typifies crimes resulting

from racial or color prejudice (Law No. 7,716/1989), until a specific law is enacted. The Supreme Court clarified that this law does not apply when the right to freedom of expression concerns religious freedom, but only if it does not constitute hate speech, incitement to discrimination, or violence against these marginalized groups.

In its reasoning for this ruling, the Supreme Federal Court (STF) stated that it constitutes an unconstitutional omission on the part of the National Congress to subject homosexuals, transgender people, and other members of the LGBTI+ community to serious offenses against their fundamental rights, due to the unreasonable exceeding of the time necessary to implement the constitutional mandates of criminalization established by the constitutional text (article 5, items XLI and XLII). Therefore, freedom of expression cannot be used to promote hate speech or acts of intolerance against the LGBTI+ community. Finally, the Supreme Federal Court issued the following thesis: (STF ADO 26/DF)

I - Until a law is enacted by the National Congress to implement the criminalization mandates defined in items XLI and XLII of article 5 of the Constitution of the Republic, homophobic and transphobic conduct, real or alleged, involving hateful aversion to someone's sexual orientation or gender identity, as they translate into expressions of racism, understood in its social dimension, are subject, by identity of reason and through typical adaptation, to the primary precepts of incrimination defined in Law No. 7,716, of 08/01/1989, also constituting, in the case of intentional homicide, a circumstance that qualifies it, as it constitutes a vile motive (Penal Code, art. 121, § 2, I, "in fine"); II - The criminal repression of homophobia and transphobia does not reach, restrict, or limit the exercise of religious freedom, regardless of the professed denomination, whose faithful and ministers (priests, pastors, rabbis, mullahs or Muslim clerics and leaders or celebrants of Afro-Brazilian religions, among others) are guaranteed the right to preach and disseminate, freely, through words, images, or any other means, their thoughts and to express their convictions in accordance with what is contained in their sacred books and codes, as well as the right to teach according to their doctrinal and/or theological orientation, being able to seek and win proselytes and practice acts of worship and respective liturgy, regardless of the space, public or private, of their individual or collective action, provided that such manifestations do not constitute hate speech, understood as those expressions that incite discrimination, hostility, or violence against people because of their sexual orientation or gender identity; III - The concept of racism, understood in its social dimension, extends beyond strictly biological or phenotypic aspects, as it results, as a manifestation of power, from a historical-cultural construction motivated by the objective of justifying inequality and aimed at ideological control, political domination, social subjugation, and the denial of the otherness, dignity, and humanity of those who, because they are part of a vulnerable group (LGBTI+) and do not belong to the stratum that holds a hegemonic position in a given social structure, are considered strange and different, degraded to the condition of marginals of the legal order, exposed, as a consequence of odious inferiorization and perverse stigmatization, to an unjust and harmful situation of exclusion from the general system of legal protection.

Indeed, the decision in this case is highly relevant with regard to fundamental rights. This is because the Supreme Court established limits to the right to freedom of expression and the right to religious freedom in relation to the right to self-determination; that is, freedom of expression and religious freedom cannot infringe upon the free sexual orientation and gender identity that each human being possesses. Furthermore, the Supreme Federal Court filled a normative gap and applied Law No. 7,716 of 1989 to protect the LGBTI+ community against the violation of their rights.

In this way, the Supreme Court not only limited the right to freedom of expression, but also established the repressive norm to be applied in case of violation of the freedom of sexual orientation or gender identity, that is, it broadened the normative protection to marginalized groups.

3.6. Criminal Action (AP)

In Criminal Action No. 1,044/DF, judged on April 20, 2022, the Supreme Federal Court analyzed the right to freedom of expression in relation to a federal deputy who had been accused of several criminal offenses, including: *i* – incitement to animosity between the Armed Forces and the STF; *ii* – the attempt to impede the free exercise of the Powers of the Union; and *iii* – the practice of coercion during the course of the proceedings. The defendant invoked in his defense the right to freedom of expression and parliamentary immunity. (STF/CNJ, 2024, p. 211).

Upon analyzing the case, the Supreme Federal Court (STF) decided that "freedom of expression does not permit the propagation of hate speech and ideas contrary to the constitutional order and the rule of law." Furthermore, it was established that parliamentary immunity, despite being a constitutional guarantee, only applies when the statements made by the political agent "are connected to the performance of the legislative function or are made by reason of it, and cannot be used as a true protective shield for the practice of illicit activities." (STF Appeal No. 1,044/DF).

This process stands out for two key factors: *i* – freedom of expression was discussed within the context of a criminal action, meaning that the constitutional prerogative that should be used for the free dissemination of ideas can, if misused, lead to the commission of crimes; and *ii* – freedom of expression does not constitute a safe conduct for the commission of crimes, that is, the agent, under the guise of exercising this principle so dear to the Democratic Rule of

Law, cannot use it as an instrument to harm or attempt to destroy the democratic regime itself and the precepts contained in the Constitution.

Therefore, in the judgment of Criminal Action No. 1,044/DF, the Supreme Federal Court established important guidelines on the right to freedom of expression, limiting it in terms of its scope and content, and preventing abuses by its holders, since they must respect constitutional values and the legal system as a whole.

CONCLUSION

This article analyzed freedom of expression in the current jurisprudence of the Brazilian Supreme Federal Court. The first part discussed freedom of expression in the 1988 Federal Constitution, a prerogative inherent to the Democratic Rule of Law, provided for in several articles of the Magna Carta, such as Article 5, sections IV, VI, and IX, as well as Article 200. The second part examined freedom of expression in relation to other constitutional rights, since conflicts may arise. This is because, as freedom of expression is a constitutional principle, its application may clash with other precepts of a constitutional nature, requiring a balancing of interests by the interpreter.

In turn, the last part dealt with important rulings of the Supreme Federal Court on the subject, such as the judgment of Habeas Corpus No. 82424, in which it was established that freedom of expression does not authorize the dissemination of hate speech or incitement to racism, nor homophobic speeches, according to ADO No. 26, as well as attempts to obstruct the free exercise of the Powers of the Union or against the existence of the Democratic Rule of Law, among other relevant judgments.

It should be noted that the right to freedom of expression can be challenged in conjunction with other constitutional legal rights through various procedural instruments, such as habeas corpus (HC), extraordinary appeal (RE), action for non-compliance with a fundamental precept (ADPF), direct action of unconstitutionality (ADI), direct action of unconstitutionality by omission (ADO), criminal action (AP), etc. In other words, the individual rights enshrined in the Constitution can be assessed by the Supreme Federal Court in various procedural scenarios, and their use is not limited to specific actions or attributed solely to certain public authorities.

Thus, freedom of expression is a fundamental right enshrined in the 1988 Federal Constitution; however, it is not intended to violate other fundamental rights of equal standing, nor to attempt to annihilate democracy, institutions, or disrupt the existing legal order.

Therefore, although freedom of expression is a right, it is not absolute or unlimited and must be exercised in accordance with the other prerogatives and values existing in the Constitution.

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